

Product-Service Systems Design with Functions and Activities

Methodological Framework and Case Studies

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Abstract: Product-Service Systems (PSS) have recently been of central attention for effective provision of diverse values. In this paper, a methodological framework for PSS design is proposed based on functions and activities. The proposed PSS design framework includes the following six steps: requirement identification and value targeting, stakeholder activity design, PSS function modeling, function-activity mapping and PSS concept generation, PSS concept detailing and PSS concept prototyping. In the proposed PSS design framework, requirements and values of various stakeholders are identified via life-cycle step analysis, and the various activities of stakeholders are defined and their relationships are analyzed via service blueprint approach. In PSS function modeling, overall function of PSS fulfilling target values is defined with the specification of service providers and receivers. The decomposition approach is then applied to obtain sub-functions and sub-providers/receivers. Then, PSS concepts are generated via the mapping between activities and functions, and they are compared with the introduction of a modified service blueprint. Sample case studies are conducted to validate the proposed PSS design framework.

Key words: Product-Service Systems (PSS), PSS Design Framework, Function, Activity

1. Introduction

Product-Service Systems (PSS) have recently drawn significant attentions since they could address diverse values of consumers and create new market with more profits by providing integrated solutions of products and services. PSS have firstly been introduced by Goedkoop et al. to simultaneously consider ecological and economic issues, and they defined PSS as a marketable set of products and services, jointly capable of fulfilling a user's need [1]. They also addressed several strengths of PSS including value creation with quality and comfort, customizing and delivery of the offer to clients, cost reduction in initial investment by sharing, leasing and hiring, lower environmental load, and so forth. Mont also defined PSS as a system of products, services, supporting networks and infrastructure that is designed to satisfy customer needs and have a lower environmental impact than traditional business models [2][3]. In addition, other definition on PSS was proposed by Manzini as an integrated body of products and services and communication strategies that was conceived, developed and promoted by (a network of) actors to generate values for society [4].

As previously defined, PSS includes several product elements and service elements that are closely related to each other. A schematic diagram of the generation of a PSS from a single product is shown in Fig. 1. A product P

is further divided into several product elements P_i . New product elements P_j can be added, and new values V_k are identified. Then, new service elements S can be added and combined with product elements in an appropriate fashion to achieve the identified values. As a result, a PSS can be generated.

Fig. 1 Schematic Diagram of Generation of PSS [5]

The evolution from a single product to PSS is one particular example to generate PSS. In general, values could play an important role to generate the PSS by being associated with functions. The functions could be later mapped to product and service elements to result in the PSS with diverse connections among them. Typical examples of PSS can be the Velo’V that is the French bike rental system and an automated teller machine (ATM). The pictures of these examples are shown in Fig. 2. These PSS provides the combined set of product and service to meet specific users’ needs, and can realize new value proposition.

Fig. 2 Typical PSS Examples

Meanwhile, the development of the methodological framework for effective PSS design was initiated by Morelli in a design discipline [6]. In his framework, the procedural steps for PSS design were proposed such as value proposition, market analysis, product/service definition, use-case analysis, tentative architecture, test and final definition, and the case study on an urban telecenter was conducted to validate the proposed framework. The design process of products and services considering life-cycle issues was studied by Aurich et al., and it included the design process for technical services in relation with products and the concept of process modularization with selecting, combining and adapting appropriate process modules [7][8]. Matzen and McAlone introduced the activity modeling cycle (AMC) method as a tool for conceptualizing PSS development to address many associated issues, and they conducted the case study on service delivery in the container ship industry to examine its effectiveness [9]. They also studied the structured modeling framework to differentiate and categorize tasks of

PSS development towards product/service oriented business with considering the case of maritime equipment [10].

Shimomura's group has conducted on substantial studies on the development of service design methodologies in the service engineering research [11][12][13][14][15]. The service model including several sub-models of flow model, scope model, view model and scenario model was proposed, and a receiver state parameter (RSP) was also introduced to describe value and cost. In addition, the computer-aided design tool, referred to as Service Explorer, was also prototyped to validate their proposed service design approach. The concept of the service model was borrowed by Maussang et al. and included into their PSS design method based on agent-based value design and functional analysis [16]. They also conducted the case study on the bike rental system – Velo'v – to show the feasibility of their proposed PSS design framework. In their more recent work, their PSS design method has been improved by additionally incorporating users' activity analysis, operation sequence and concept evaluations in the early design phase [17].

Although considerable researches to develop effective methods for designing PSS have been conducted, the systematic approaches organically addressing functions and activities of PSS have seldom been studied, which could be of much significance in the case of PSS design. Functions could be considered as the natural term to realize values to satisfy the customer needs and requirements. A number of researches on functional analysis and modeling have been carried out in the domain of product design. The format of verb-noun pair to express functions was firstly introduced by Miles [18] and Rodnacker [19]. They also introduced the concept of flows of energy, material and information to complete functional representations when describe product functionality. Then, Koller proposed twelve basic functions, and Hundal modified Koller's work by producing function and flow classes [20][21]. Szykman and Stone conducted researches to provide the universal functional languages have been attempted by proposing the standardized sets of functions and flows [22][23], and their works were later reconciled by Hirtz et al. to result in the Functional Basis [24].

On the other hand, a number of parallel research works for developing functional modeling techniques could be led by other researchers. Umeda and Tomiyama introduced the concept of the Function-Behavior-State modeling which reflected designers' intent and product behavior as the realization of the function of product [25]. Then, Gero has been a leading researcher to establish the Function-Behavior-Structure framework in the course of product design, and he even extended his framework into the situated Function-Behavior-Structure to reflect dynamic context [26][27]. In Gero's research works, the term of behavior was considered to be more detailed description of high-level functionality.

In PSS design, service activities should be appropriately addressed due to its nature of service elements. In addition, the stakeholders including service providers and service receivers should be properly defined to complete the descriptions on their interactions based on activities in PSS. The service blueprint method, which was originally proposed by Shostack, was used to describe stakeholders' interactions and their activities in the service design process [28].

Even though many research works to study PSS design methods, there have been no such comprehensive and systematic approach for effective design of PSS. Therefore, this paper discusses the development of a methodological framework for PSS design considering functions and activities. This proposed PSS design framework consists of the following six steps: requirement identification and value targeting, stakeholder activity design, PSS function modeling, function-activity mapping and PSS concept generation, PSS concept detailing

and PSS concept prototyping. In the proposed PSS design framework, requirements of various stakeholders are identified via life-cycle step analysis and they are linked with economic, ecological and experience values. Then, the various activities of stakeholders are defined and their relationships are analyzed via service blueprint approach. In PSS function modeling, overall function of PSS fulfilling target values is defined with the specification of service providers and receivers. The decomposition approach is then applied to obtain sub-functions and sub-providers/receivers. Then, PSS concepts are generated via the mapping between activities and functions, and they are compared with the introduction of a modified service blueprint. Sample case studies are conducted to validate the proposed PSS design framework.

2. PSS Design Framework

In PSS design framework proposed in this paper, there are six procedural phases such as (1) Requirement Identification and Value Targeting, (2) Stakeholder Activity Design, (3) PSS Function Modeling, (4) Function-Activity Mapping and PSS Concept Generation, (5) PSS Concept Detailing and (6) PSS Concept Prototyping. Fig. 3 shows the overview of PSS design framework. The detailed explanations and descriptions on each design phase are followed in the next several sub-sections.

Fig. 3 Product-Service Systems (PSS) Design Framework

2.1. Requirement Identification and Value Targeting

To effectively design PSS, requirements, needs and values of various stakeholders should be firstly analyzed and identified. To extract and address potential requirements of associated stakeholders, the life-cycle step analysis is conducted. A graphical information model is adopted, which includes life-cycle steps, related stakeholders and their needs and wants in an integrated fashion. The schematic diagram of the life-cycle step analysis is given in Fig. 4.

As can be seen Fig. 4, life-cycle steps are divided into pre, during and post phases, and they are expressed as a circular form, which implies the notion of a repetitive cycle of life-cycle steps. For each step, associated

stakeholders are identified and located near step nodes. The primary stakeholders that are directly related to the life-cycle steps are located closer to nodes, and other stakeholders are then located outside the primary ones. The needs and wants related to each stakeholder are described in each step node. The needs and wants addressed in Fig. 4 are later interpreted into requirements and critical target values, which will be pursued in the subsequent design phases.

Fig. 4 Schematic Diagram of Life-Cycle Step Analysis

2.2. Stakeholder Activity Design

In this design phase, specific stakeholders related to PSS to be realized are defined and their activities are designed. The service blueprint method is introduced to design activities and to analyze their relations. The service blueprint method was originally proposed by Shostack to describe service roadmaps [28]. The service blueprint can tangibly and visually document how and where service receivers and service providers interact.

After arranging possible activities of stakeholders in the service blueprint, each activity is detailed by reflecting its various contexts. To appropriately describe activities in more detail, the context-based activity model is proposed, and its schematic diagram is given in Fig. 5.

As can be seen in Fig. 5, seven elements are defined such as Activity, Actor, Object, Tool, Event, Context and Environment. The element of “activity” is a goal-oriented behavior of “actors”, and the “actor” is composed of “active agent”, “passive agent” and “third-party agent”. The “object” is the subject of “activity” and “tool” is a means to accomplish the goal. The element of “event” drives and changes the “activity” in the various “context”. The element of “context” consists of goal context, relevant structure, physical context and psychological context. The “activity” occurs in the “environment”, which includes inner space, outer space and virtual space.

The context-based activity model can lead to the generation of various scenarios of PSS. The activities that are sequentially arranged in the service blueprint have a few activity concepts based on different contexts. Then, several PSS scenarios can be obtained by selecting a specific activity concept from each activity and combining them. The schematic diagram describing PSS scenario generation is shown in Fig. 6. Several alternative PSS scenarios can be effectively obtained with the scenario generation template given in Fig. 6.

Fig. 5 Context-Based Activity Model

Fig. 6 Schematic Diagram of PSS Scenario Generation

2.3 PSS Function Modeling

The design phase of PSS function modeling covers the definition of overall function of PSS that most effectively realize the target values identified from the previous phase, and its decomposition into a number of critical sub-functions to simplify design problem and to innovatively integrate fragmentary design solutions. In PSS function modeling, service usually requires providers and receivers and its quality and contents highly depends on their interactions [29]. Therefore, the information of service providers and receivers should be properly represented in PSS function blocks.

The schematic diagram of the overall function block of PSS is given in Fig. 7. As can be seen in Fig. 7, three flows – energy, material and information – can build logical connections among function blocks. The service provider and receiver are expressed as folded lines in upper left corner and lower right corner of the function block, respectively. The overall function given in Fig. 7 can further be decomposed into a number of critical sub-

functions. The sub-function blocks are connected by associated flows based on their causal and logical relations, and these relations can be used to define the PSS function modules by grouping a couple of blocks. The service provider and receiver can also be decomposed into sub-service providers and sub-service receivers, and they are appropriately assigned to each sub-function block. Each sub-function block and function module can be linked to possible product and service elements to complete PSS concepts by innovatively configuring them.

Fig. 7 Schematic Diagram of Functional Modeling of PSS

2.4. Function-Activity Mapping and PSS Concept Generation

When generating PSS concepts, functions, stakeholders, activities and product/service elements should be considered as a whole. The functions, stakeholders and activities can further be decomposed, and the lowest level of each entity can be linked together with product and service elements to form a specific PSS concept. The mapping between sub-functions and sub-activities is completed via associated stakeholders, and product and service elements are assigned to sub-functions to complete PSS concept generation and representation.

The modified service blueprint method is proposed by inserting the layer of function between customer activity layer and on-stage service provider activity layer. The layer of function can represent the interactions among stakeholders. Fig. 8 shows the schematic diagram of the modified service blueprint. With the modified service blueprint, alternative PSS concepts can be compared by mapping different activities conducted by different stakeholders to realize same functions.

Fig. 8 Schematic Form of Modified Service Blueprint

2.5. PSS Concept Detailing

The PSS concepts can be more elaborated by linking the product and service elements with other various stakeholders. The inter-relations among product and service elements as well as their relations with outer stakeholders are analyzed and defined. In this design phase, designers can design the detailed operations of PSS by identifying specific product and service elements with associated stakeholders. In addition, the operation sequence of detailed PSS concept can also be described by considering sequential flows of operational activities with their relations with product/service elements and constraints.

2.6. PSS Concept Prototyping

The final phase of PSS design process is the concept prototyping. In this phase, the detailed PSS concept is translated into a tentative prototype of PSS. The PSS prototype can be physical architecture or story/scenario reflecting crucial functional requirements and their attributes. With the PSS prototype, the proposed PSS concept can be evaluated and tested for satisfying specific customer requirements and values.

3. Case Study – Clothes TakeIN PSS

As an illustrative example, Clothes TakeIN PSS was developed at the Creative Design Institute by following the proposed PSS design framework in this paper. TakeIN is the PSS series name for providing methods to motivate desirable reuse of products, which indicates taking them back into use rather than just throwing away.

For the life-cycle step of reuse of clothes, there exist products such as used clothes bins located in shabby corner of back alley streets. Considering stakeholders' activities involved with these bins, would it be happy to go out to donate clothes into a bin located in such a secluded corner of the back alley, for instance, in rainy night? Sometimes, you could witness stray cats coming out such bins. The scenario of such experience in the donation of used clothes is depicted in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9 Schematic representation of current state of shabby used clothes bins and related service activities as the clothes are transferred from the donator to the receiver.

Negative reactive emotional experience values obtained from the current shabby used clothes bins in such physical contexts would reduce your active emotional experience value needed for your voluntary donation of clothes. Those clothes collected from such bins have been dealt with like trash and some useful clothes could be selected by laborious efforts of human operators. After identifying those negative value attributes encountered in the current used clothes bins, and design strategies were set to convert those negative experience values into positive ones.

Therefore, the new PSS concept promoting experience values of donators and collectors was generated by designing their activities. When considering the clothes TakeIN PSS station located in community centers or convenience stores, this concept could lead to a variety of new activities of donators. In other words, if we change the physical contexts, new service activities promoting specific target values could be effectively generated. For example, we could also create activities and attitudes similar to those related to giving clothes that have been worn by his/her son to nephew as a gift in the new concept. Therefore, the activities of packaging of clothes were added to donators' activities. In addition, donator's activities of cleaning and repairing of used clothes were added in the new concept. The scenario describing the new clothes TakeIN PSS is schematically shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10 Schematic representation of cleaning, repairing and packaging service activities of donators have been designed in as well as clothes TakeIN PSS Station with features affording such activities.

The activities added in the new concept were linked with functions that were decomposed from the overall function of “collect and supply clothes”. These relationships between activities and functions were represented in the modified service blueprint, and the current used clothes bins and proposed new PSS concept were compared and analyzed.

The functional requirements allowing specific activities should be realized as features in the prototype. The sketch of clothes TakeIN PSS station is given in the upper right corner of Fig. 10. In the clothes TakeIN PSS

station, the activity of inputting the information of donating clothes is done with small screen located in upper left area of the station. Afterwards, the guideline for packaging of clothes is provided in the big screen after taking photo of clothes with a camera located top part of the big screen. When packaging clothes, donators used the appropriate packaging box provided by the box provision module of the station. Then, donators print a bar coded sticker including the information of donated clothes and attach the sticker to the box. The boxes containing donated clothes are input to the input slot having the bar code identification module, and they are stored in the storage unit located in the lower part of the station.

We also considered the affordance design in the prototype. For example, the upper left plate of the station was designed to have appropriate height and shape to afford the activities of placing donators' belongings such as a bag.

4. Conclusions

This paper proposed a systematic PSS design framework based on functions and activities. The proposed PSS design process includes the following six phases: (1) requirement identification and value targeting, (2) stakeholder activity design, (3) PSS function modeling, (4) function-activity mapping and PSS concept generation, (5) PSS concept detailing and (6) PSS concept prototyping.

In phase 1, the requirements of various stakeholders were identified via life-cycle step analysis, and they were linked with economic, ecological and experience values. Then, various activities of stakeholders were defined and their relationships were analyzed via service blueprint approach in phase 2. In addition, the activities were more elaborated with context-based activity modeling, and several PSS scenarios could be generated by combining activities. In the phase of PSS function modeling, overall function of PSS fulfilling target values was defined with the specification of service providers and receivers. The decomposition approach was then applied to obtain sub-functions and sub-providers/receivers. In phase 4, functions, stakeholders, activities and product/service elements were mapped together to generate and represent alternative PSS concepts and the modified service blueprint method was proposed to compare generated PSS concepts. The rough PSS concepts were embodied in the phase 5 by relating product/service elements and stakeholders and providing detailed sequence of operational activities. Finally, in the phase 6, either physical or story-based prototype for PSS concept is developed for testing and evaluation.

In order to validate the proposed PSS design framework, the case study on designing "Clothes TakeIN PSS" was conducted. The results from the case study confirmed the usefulness of the proposed PSS design framework. In addition, in the case study, the design activities of each phase have been occurred in an iterative way rather than a sequential one, which is usual in general design sessions.

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